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ACADEMIC SUPERVISION AS A TOOL FOR FUTURE CIVIL SERVANTS' PROFESSIONAL IMAGE DEVELOPMENT

КУРАТОРСТВО ЯК ІНСТРУМЕНТ РОЗВИТКУ ПРОФЕСІЙНОГО ІМІДЖУ МАЙБУТНІХ ДЕРЖАВНИХ СЛУЖБОВЦІВ

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Балан О.С., Шепель М.Є., Сита Є.М. Кураторство як інструмент розвитку професійного іміджу майбутніх державних службовців. Науково-методична стаття.

Стаття присвячена кураторству у ВНЗ як інструменту розвитку професійного іміджу майбутніх державних службовців. Метою статті виступає визначення ролі кураторства у розвитку професійного іміджу майбутніх державних службовців. Запропоновано модель розвитку професійного іміджу майбутніх службовців через кураторство. Метою моделі виступає розвиток конкурентоспроможного фахівця через формування професійного іміджу. Виховна робота включає: національно-патріотичне виховання, морально-духовне виховання, громадянсько-правове виховання, естетичне виховання, професійне виховання. Засобами імплементації ми обрали кураторські години, круглі столи, дискусії, зустрічі із фахівцями та стрейкхолдерами як онлайн так і офлайн. Результат впровадження моделі вбачаємо формування конкурентно-спроможного фахівця, з власним професійним іміджем. Визначено, що розвиток іміджу майбутніх державних службовців є складним та багатоаспектним процесом. Важлива роль відводиться кураторству, яке здійснюється через всі аспекти виховання майбутніх фахівців державної служби.

Ключові слова: кураторство, вищий навчальний заклад, виховна робота, імідж, професійний імідж, майбутні державні службовці

Balan O.S., Shepel M.Ye., Syta Ye.M. Academic Supervision as a Tool for Future Civil Servants' Professional Image Development. Scientific and methodical article.

The article is dedicated to the academic supervision at universities as a tool for future civil servants' professional image development. The aim of the article is to determine the role of academic supervision in the future civil servants' professional image development. The model of developing the future civil servants' professional image through academic supervision has been proposed. The aim the model is a competitive specialist development through the professional image formation. Educational work includes: national and patriotic education, moral and spiritual education, civil and legal education, aesthetic education, vocational education. We have chosen curatorial hours, round tables, discussions, meetings with experts and stakeholders both online and offline as the means of implementation. The result of the implementation of the model we regard in the competitive specialists' formation with his/her own professional image. It has been determined that the future civil servants' professional image development is a complex and multifaceted process. Academic supervision plays an important role in all aspects of educating the future specialists of the Civil Service.

Keywords: academic supervision, a higher education institution, educational work, image, professional image, future civil servants

The development of Ukraine as an independent and democratic state puts forward our educational institutions new challenges and requirements. An important factor of the education process changes is the integration of our country to the European Union, strengthening relations with developed European countries, introducing new technologies. The Law of Ukraine "On Higher Education" states that the educational process is an intellectual, creative activity in the field of higher education and science, which is carried out in a higher education institution (scientific institution) through a system of scientific and methodological and pedagogical activities, acquisition, increase and use of knowledge, skills and other competencies among students, as well as a harmoniously developed personality formation [1]. Thus, it is important now to train a competitive specialist who not only skilfully uses professional knowledge and skills of interpersonal interaction, but also loves his/her country and his/her people, preserves its traditions, i.e., cares about the image of his/her country. In the

context of the latter, educational work as one of the teaching and educational process components acquires special relevance in a higher education institution.

The Concept of Civic Education in Ukraine states that the teaching and educational process should be an integral part of the entire educational process and focus on the spiritual values of the Ukrainian people (national self-consciousness, identity, distinctiveness, honour, unity, freedom), universal values, in particular moral and ethical (dignity, honesty, justice, respect for the family institution, care, respect for themselves and others) and socio-political (freedom, democracy, cultural diversity, respect for native language and culture, patriotism, respect for the environment, respect for the law, responsibility and solidarity) [2]. The Ukrainian labour market presents a wide range of different specialties (economic, technical, technological, pedagogical, humanitarian), which are the vocational training for future professionals. In our opinion, in modern conditions the vocational training of future specialists in the field of civil service, who are able to represent our country in the international arena, is becoming important. In the process of studying at university, future civil servants' public image development becomes relevant. Academic supervision has a special role in this process.

Analisis of recent researches and publications

Both Ukrainian and foreign scientists dedicated their studies to the issues of academic mentoring: T. Osypova, I. Bartienieva, O. Bila, L. Bilousova, I. Bohdanova, S. Brychok, I. Buzhyna, S. Vitvytska, V. Volkova, M. Holubieva, N. Holiardyk, V. Hrytsaniuk, A. Denysenko, A. Zhulkivska, A. Ilchenko, N. Kuzmenko, S. Kuchyn, O. Luchaninova, Ye. Olkhovskiy, K. Churpii, Jh. Lodge, T. Loos, A. Tenorio, T. Tenorio. N. Barna, L. Danylchuk, I. Kolosovska, S. Kolosok, Yu. Padafet, O. Gaivoronskaya, O. Kapustyuk, I. Krynickiy, O. Myttseva, G. Popova, L. Serheieva, S. Conway, L. Dobelli, J. Hickey devoted their works to specialists' image in general and civil service specialists in particular.

Unsolved aspects of the problem

The analysis of the presented above research has shown that today the issue of academic supervision as a tool for developing the of future civil servants' public image development is not given enough attention, which has prompted us to write this study.

The aim of the article is to highlight the role of academic supervision in future civil servants' professional image development.

The main part

It should be noted that there are several English equivalents for the Ukrainian term "kurator": "supervisor", "tutor" and "mentor". Let's consider them in more detail.

Supervisor is considered as someone who is in charge of an activity, a place, or a group of people such as workers or students [3].

Tutor is a teacher paid to work privately with one student or a small group [4].

Mentor is an experienced person in a company, university, etc. who trains and advises new employees or students [5].

Thus, Odesa scientists T. Osipova, I. Barteneva, O. Bila, I. Bogdanova, I. Buzhina do not single out the concepts of "supervisor", "tutor" and "mentor". According to their position, supervisor (tutor, mentor) of students' academic group is a mentor and organizer, educator and consultant for applicants for the group. It is intended to guide the educational work of the group, to develop students' activity, independence, initiative, sense of responsibility and interest in learning, to be constantly in business communication with the student group, to know each student well, which gives him the opportunity to influence the team as a whole, and for each student in particular [6, p.254]. Taking into account the scientists' position we will take the term "supervisor" for the equivalent for the Ukrainian term "kurator" as it mostly reflects Ukrainian lecturers' activity.

The researcher O. Luchaninova notes that in accordance with the European educational standards, today the academic group supervisor performs the functions of a student's facilitator, coordinator of educational activities, provides spiritual and cultural support for his/her development as a person, i.e., is a key figure of subjective relations with the student in the educational process. The scientist emphasizes that in many domestic universities' lecturers fill their activities with new content, while also acting as an academic consultant, tutor (a supervisor for the student or the students' group), an educational programme curator. Such activities are aimed primarily at the education quality. O. Luchaninova notes that in this case one can observe a contradictory position taken by a certain part of the teaching staff of the university: providing only educational services to students and complete denial of pedagogical influence on the student's personality. According to the scholar, the falsity of this position can be refuted by the fact that nowadays education itself is a value. The lecturer, who often also serves as the academic group supervisor, has a responsibility to create the conditions for the student to become a professional [7, p.125].

Comparing the activities of the academic group supervisor of the Ukrainian university and the tutor of the British university, M. Golubeva and A. Zhulkivska claim that the supervisor is not only a higher institution lecturer, i.e. also carries out educational activity itself, and also as a supervisor and, influences the student youth by means of carrying out various educational measures and engages it in self-examination, promotes establishment of friendly, moral, humanistic relations among students; acts as a mediator in the student' interaction with the academic staff and management of the higher education institution. Thus, the tutor can be characterized as a special

pedagogical position, formed historically and provides the individual educational programmes development for students, as well as accompanies them in the process of individual learning in school, higher education, additional and continuing education [8, p.19].

In foreign studies, the term "tutor" means a whose key function is to ensure basic contact with students, as well as consistent administrative, academic and career activities, using the latest methods and technologies to interact with lecturers and the education institution [9, p.16].

Having experience as the academic groups' supervisors in higher education institutions, in our study we will consider the activity of the academic group supervisor in the educational process in general, and the future civil servants' professional image development in particular.

Analysing the academic group supervisor's activities, V. Levchenko in a supervisor's personality considers a professor or a lecturer of an educational institution attached to a particular academic group to monitor and control the students' educational and extracurricular activities and provide them with informational, organizational, psychological and pedagogical assistance in solving various issues. According to the researcher, the supervisor's activity is primarily focused on solving the key task, i.e., to support and strengthen the students' motivation for vocational education, to promote their active participation in the educational process [10, p.126].

The academic group supervisor's educational work involves the presence of several blocks that are embodied simultaneously and interconnected.

Table 1. The Academic Group Supervisor's Educational Work

Block	Description
Education of patriotism	It provides creating the clear guidelines for students' national devotion, involvement in the study and multiplication of rich traditions of the national intelligentsia, development of the Ukrainian nation, its historical consciousness, traditions, Ukrainian science and culture.
Teaching and educational work	It provides the importance of proper education, transferring interest for the course he/she teaches (if the supervisor teaches in his/her group).
Psychological and pedagogical work	It is planned by the supervisor, taking into account its results analysis.
Scientific and methodological work	It is built on the basis of constant pedagogical and scientific research (the students' involvement in scientific research clubs, preparation for speeches at scientific conferences).

Source: compiled by authors on materials [10].

According to A. Ilchenko, the supervisor's educational work in the student academic group is a holistic and orderly set of regularly constructed, interconnected components, which together contribute to the personality's professional becoming and development, formation of his/her life position, skills for independent work and team work [11].

N. Kuzmenko claims that the supervisor has a significant educational impact on the students' professional interest formation and related self-affirmation and self-actualization, promotes knowledge and skills development, the worldview formation. The academic group unity according to the scientist, will be only if the supervisor is able to form in the students a positive attitude towards each other, friendly relations in the team, a friendly atmosphere that promotes a full educational process [12, p.330].

In order to become students as professionals, it is important that the supervisor adheres to certain functions, namely (Table 2).

In this context, the academic group supervisor's competence is of great important. The supervisor's competence relates to his/her personal traits, skills and abilities, and also requires not only sufficient professional experience in higher education, but also at least a year of work at the university where he/she is tasked to supervise a group of students. We support B. Hrytsanyuk's position that the supervisor should be a specialist in the field of his/her students' specialty, as well as to teach one of the lecture courses or conduct seminars / practical classes in the academic group [14].

In our opinion, the supervisor's observance of the abovementioned functions and his/her professional competence are important tools in the development and formation of future professionals' image in general and future civil servants in particular.

In the framework of our research, the definition of the phenomena "a civil servant", "image", "a specialist's image", "professional image" and "public image" becomes important.

According to the Law of Ukraine "On Civil Service", a civil servant is a citizen of Ukraine who holds a civil service position in a public authority, other public authority, its staff (secretariat) (hereinafter – the public authority), receives a salary from the state budget and exercises the powers established for this position, directly related to the performance of tasks and functions of such public authority, as well as adheres to the civil service principles [15].

Image is the way that something or someone is thought of by other people; the reputation that a person, organization, product, etc. has, including the characteristics, appearance, etc. that they are known for [16].

L. Danilchuk states that the term "image" was not used in domestic professional language practice until 1992, which led to its simplified perception and uncertainty of the scientific apparatus. The scientist notes that the

concept of "image" is a holistic, well-defined, stable and renewed in the mass and / or individual consciousness of the image of the object, which is created to transform it into society [17, p.7].

According to O. Gaivoronskaya, in psychology there are two main approaches to understanding the image. The first one considers it as a purposefully constructed specialists' image, which should influence the choice of the electorate. The second one is as an image-representation, which is the result of previous spontaneous perception of a politician's real personal qualities, his/her political activities or deliberately attributed to someone by the politician qualities and properties [18, p. 4]

N. Barna notes that the word "image" is not synonymous with the word "appearance". Image is defined as the expressive, expressive side of the appearance [19, p.16].

Image contains not only natural personality traits, but also specially designed, created, formed. Other definitions emphasize that the image is largely determined by a person's objective characteristics, in particular the person's image is determined by its psychological type and compliance with the demands of time and society. Both are certainly correct [19, p.17].

Table 2. The Supervisor's Functions

Function	Description
Educational	Influence on the students' emotional, volitional, intellectual and physical qualities formation, based on a system of various educational activities
Organizational	Initiation by the supervisor of educational activities, stimulation and motivation, organization and control
Coordinating	Coordinating the group's activities with the dean's office, departments, rectorate The academic group supervisor's ability to direct the educational efforts of teachers, parents, members of the public to positive results in the students' education
Socially-oriented	Directing educational activities to develop the students' scientific worldview, professional qualities and active life position
Research-analytical	Diagnosing personal education levels, studying the students' motives, interests and needs of educational and cognitive activity, social and living conditions, health status, level of success, etc.; studying the students' internal world and possibilities, drawing up their development programmes
Informational	The supervisor's ability to accumulate knowledge of the theory and methods of the educational process, to be a good educator, a model of pedagogical experience, an authoritative adviser in the process of finding a variety of information, a mentor on any problematic issues;
Social	Studying by the supervisor the objective and subjective factors that influence the personality's development; social life skills correlation aimed at successful entry of the students into the structure of modern life and production
Guiding (moral and educational)	Directing the students to make life choices in accordance with moral and legal norms, forming humane relationships in the student environment, enriching their experience with historical and life examples worth following
Incentive	Creating the atmosphere of psychological and pedagogical support in the group, which promotes young person's self-affirmation, his/her potential realization
Communicative	Creating a friendly microclimate in the group, ensuring positive changes in interpersonal relationships

Source: compiled by authors on materials [8, 13].

Image refers to a group of socio-psychological phenomena. So, it obeys all the basic principles of social psychology. Among the most important are the following:

- a person is a social being, he/she is extremely dependent on his/her group and social environment;
- human behaviour in the group is determined by stereotypes, i.e., generalized and simplified ideas;
- the attitude of the whole group to a particular person significantly affects how he/she will be perceived by individual members;
- in different groups, the same person may have a different reputation and, consequently, appropriate behaviour;
- a positive attitude of the group to the individual contributes to the solution of its problems [19, p.19].

The specialist's image has the character of a stereotype, i.e., a simplified, not multifaceted image. It should not have a large number of characteristics. Its study should be carried out for scheme with a limited number of components:

- manifestations of the specialist's personal traits and characteristics;
- the behaviour and nature of relationships in the workforce;
- the professional activity results [20, p.224].

As civil servants' activity is connected with publicity it is necessary to define the concepts of public image and professional image.

Public image is the opinion that many people have of a person [21].

Professional image is a multifaceted, interdisciplinary concept, the essence of which synthesizes the social image of the characteristics of a certain socio-professional group in accordance with the expectations of society. Simultaneously it is a holistic, dynamic and integrative, conditioned way for a professional activity of the subject, namely "An Individuals' Mission" positive "I-Concept" focused on the "I-Desired, Ideal" that contributes to a modern specialist's constant professional and personal self-development and self-improvement. The aim of professional image is the achievement by the prototype subject of professional and personal goals in relation to ensuring coordination of actions, mental states of participants in the labour process [22, p.196].

In our viewpoint a civil servant's public image and professional image are interconnected.

Considering the image of a civil servant I. Sergeeva notes that when it comes to the civil servant's image, in addition to external elements (business suit, appropriate hairstyle and makeup, as well as smell), it should be emphasized that important skills to enter any social environment, reduce shortcomings and highlight your best business qualities. According to the scientist, there is an international standard of civil service, based on the following attributes such as demonstration of their own uniqueness and confidence; self-satisfaction, life, environment; the behaviour of the winner and the successful person [23].

I. Krynychna defines the civil servant's image as a consciously formed image of state power in its personal dimension. From the standpoint of adequacy, the following types of image are distinguished: mirror (self-image), i.e. one's own perception of oneself or the organization, mostly positive; current (real), i.e. a person's formed image, the organization which reflects external perception and an estimation of image of the person or the organization; desirable, i.e. the image that the person or organization (state) seeks to form in the perception of citizens, is reflected in the relevant regulations governing the civil servants' activities (laws on civil service, job descriptions, ethical codes, etc.) [24].

Defining the components, the civil servant's image I. Krynychna distinguishes professionalism, psychological climate of the organization, managerial culture. To the components of the civil servants' image, we have also added the possession of soft skills, which are formed and developed by applicants during their studies at the university. In the latter, educational work in higher education plays an important role [24].

Table 3. The Component of the Civil Servant's Image

Component	Description
Professionalism	The civil servants' ability to determine, taking into account the conditions and real possibilities, the most effective ways and means of carrying out the tasks set before them within the normatively defined powers
Psychological climate of the organization	The mood of the workforce (personnel), its relatively stable psychological condition, which reflects the peculiarities of its life, moral atmosphere and relations between employees in the team
Managerial culture	The ability to work competently, professionally, proactively
Possessing soft skills	universal competencies, which are much more difficult to measure by quantitative indicators. These include: communication skills, team work abilities, critical thinking, leadership skills, conflict resolution skills.

Source: compiled by authors on materials [24].

The civil servants' image is closely related to their behaviour. There are certain requirements for the civil servants' official behaviour, which can be classified according to three different types: constituent (performance of official duties conscientiously, at a high professional level; understand that recognition, observance and protection of human and civil rights and freedoms determine the meaning and content of professional service activity; professional service activity implementation within the competence of the state body established by the Ukrainian legislation); prohibitive (observance of restrictions established by the law; do not make acts that dishonour the dignity; do not allow conflict situations capable of causing damage to the personal reputation or authority of the state body); recommendatory (manifestation of correctness in interaction with citizens; observe the established rules of public speeches and providing the official information) [25].

Thus, the future civil servants' image can be defined as the image that is formed and reproduced in the process of educational activities and future professional activities, the purpose of which is the comprehensive development and becoming of future specialists as professionals.

In our opinion, academic supervision is an important aspect in the formation and development of the future civil servants' image. According to the regulations on the supervisor of the ONPU (Odessa Polytechnic National University) academic group, the academic group supervisor should promote the creation of the healthy moral and psychological climate in the group, the normal relations establishment between students and professors and staff of the institute (faculty) and university [26].

Starting working with the academic group, each supervisor conducts a survey among students to identify the group's assets, get acquainted with the families of students, identify students' privileged categories, as well as identify problems that may arise in the process of studying at the university.

Being a scientific advisor at the largest institute of the Odessa Polytechnic National University, i.e., Institute of Economics and Management, great attention is paid to national and patriotic, moral and spiritual, civil and legal,

aesthetic, vocational education of the future civil servants. These aspects, in our opinion, constitute the future civil servants' image. The educational work model is given in the Figure 1.

As it can be seen from the Figure 1, the aim of the model is to develop a complete specialist through his/her professional image formation. All the types of the educational work are interconnected and they cannot be developed separately. The result of this model is a competitive specialist with professional and moral qualities, who has his/her own professional image.

The future civil servants are the representatives of the country in general, and cities and territorial communities in particular, much attention should be paid to the future civil servants' patriotic education through acquaintance with Ukrainian traditions and instilling respect for traditions and customs of other countries, conducting curatorial classes on patriotic issues ("24 August is the Independence Day of Ukraine", "Odessa Birthday", "The Anniversary of the Heroic Defense of Odessa", "History of My University", "The Day of Defender of Ukraine", "The Day of Dignity and Freedom", "The Day of Unity of Ukraine", "10 April Is the Day of Odessa Liberation from Fascist Invaders", "We Remember. We Win (to the Victory Day)", "Holocaust Remembrance Day", "Holodomor Remembrance Day", "Chernobyl Remembrance Day", "Our Nightingale Language (To the Day of the Ukrainian language)", "The Embroidered Shirt is the Code of the Nation").

Moral and spiritual education is carried out through a combination of principles and norms of universal morality and national and moral values, such as a student's education of as high moral personality. In this case, the students' development of as highly moral, intelligent, competitive and cultural personalities becomes important.

Figure 1. The Model of the Future Civil Servants' Professional Development Through Academic Supervision

Source: authors' own development

Civil education is aimed at forming a socially mature, responsible behaviour of the students on the basis of knowledge, norms and principles of current legislation of Ukraine, respect for the rights and freedoms of others, respect for state symbols. The students' education as citizens involves becoming patriots, i.e., people with an active civil position, focused on democratic values and freedoms, able to protect the rights and fulfil their public duties, reflected in the Constitution of Ukraine, improvement of the city, the territory of the university, preservation of the national good and the environmental protection. Legal education is carried out through the requirements for conscientious performance of their duties, compliance with the provisions and rules of internal regulations of the university, orders and instructions of the university management, as well as through invitations of lawyers, conducting round tables, debates.

The most important objectives of aesthetic education are the mature aesthetic tastes development, the ability to distinguish true aesthetic values from false, contrived, the formation of the need for aestheticization of working and living conditions. The students' aesthetic culture formation takes place both in the educational process and in extracurricular activities. Educational influence is largely realized through the students' participation in amateur art, clubs, visiting theatres, exhibitions, museums, both offline and online.

Vocational education is aimed at the students' professional self-awareness, erudition and competence formation; ability to set tasks in a certain field of professional activity and solve them creatively.

The students' education of as professionals is aimed at development of:

- deep interest, love for the chosen profession, erudition and professional competence;
- ability to set different levels of creative tasks and solve them effectively in the chosen field of future professional activity;
- willingness to make non-standard decisions and think critically;
- willingness to work in a team and resolve conflict situations;

— openness to new achievements of science and technology.

This type of education is carried out through talks, round tables, students' participation in conferences and scientific works contents, debates. Excursions to companies, meetings with stakeholders, former graduates of this specialty who studied at university play an important role in vocational education.

During the curatorial classes we also discuss with the applicants the advice of foreign experts on creating and improving the image of a professional and how it can be applied in Ukrainian practice.

Conclusions

Thus, as we can see, the future civil servants' professional image is a complex and multifaceted process. An important role in this process is played by academic supervision, which is carried out through all aspects of education (moral and spiritual, aesthetic, national and patriotic, civil and legal, vocational). But it is important to remember that civil servants' professional image improvement does not end after graduating the university. This process is aimed at continuous self-development and self-improvement. Further study becomes the problem of future civil servants' social media etiquette rules development as a part of their vocational training.

Abstract

The development of Ukraine as an independent and democratic state puts forward our educational institutions' new challenges and requirements. An important factor of the educational process changes is our country's integration to the European Union, strengthening relations with developed European countries, introducing new technologies.

The Ukrainian labour market presents a wide range of different specialties (economic, technical, technological, pedagogical, humanitarian), which are the vocational training for future professionals. In our opinion, in modern conditions the training of the future specialists in the field of civil service, who are able to represent our country in the international arena, is becoming important. In the process of studying at university, the future civil servants' public image development becomes relevant. Academic supervision has a special role in this process.

The aim of the article is to highlight the role of academic supervision in future civil servants' public image development

Having experience as academic groups supervisor in higher education institutions, in our study we have considered the activity of the academic group supervisor in the educational process of free education in general, and the future civil servants' public image development in particular.

We have noted the academic group supervisor's competence is of great important. The supervisor's competence relates to his/her personal traits, skills and abilities, and also requires not only sufficient professional experience in higher education, but also at least a year of work in the institution where he/she is tasked to supervise a group of students.

In the framework of our research, we have considered the definitions of the phenomena "a civil servant", "image", "a specialist's image", "professional image" and "public image".

The future civil servants' image can be defined as the image that is formed and reproduced in the process of educational activities and future professional activities, the purpose of which is the comprehensive development and becoming of future specialists as professionals.

Starting working with the academic group, each curator conducts a survey among applicants to identify the group's assets, get acquainted with the families of students, identify students' privileged categories, as well as identify problems that may arise in the process of studying at the university.

As scientific advisors at the largest institute of the Odessa Polytechnic National University, i.e., Institute of Economics and Management, great attention we paid to moral and spiritual, aesthetic, national and patriotic, civil and legal, vocational education of the future civil servants. These aspects, in our opinion, constitute the future civil servants' image.

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